

LUXEMBOURG HYDROGEN VALLEY

Luxembourg Hydrogen Valley [LuxHyVal] delivers integrated full-chain sustainable hydrogen ecosystem with technical, economic, social, and environmental benefits and superior replicability

Deliverable D1.1 – Project management handbook

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D1.1 Project management handbook

Executive summary

This project management handbook outlines the internal procedures that should be applied by the members of the LuxHyVal project. The procedures cover project execution, structure, administrative management and reporting, internal and external communication, and general points on the quality assurance. It contains all relevant information for the Consortium partners to refer to during the project to complete and fulfil all management, reporting, and communication tasks. Additionally, it describes relevant tools to be used for internal communication, records keeping, reporting and dissemination of relevant project materials.

This project management handbook does not cover the questions related to the project data management (covered in the Data Management Plan, Sensitive deliverable D1.2), and consequences of non-compliance of the project records/deliverables to the Grant agreement (covered by the Chapter 5 of the LuxHyVal Grant Agreement n°101111984) as does not fall under the “information the Consortium partners need to refer to during the project to complete and fulfil all management, reporting, and communication tasks”.

List of Abbreviations

AE	Associated Entity
AP	Associated Partner
BEN	Beneficiary
CA	Consortium Agreement
CHJU	Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking
COO	Coordinator
D	Deliverable
DD	Due date
DoA	Description of Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
Gen. Assem.	General Assembly
IPR	Intellectual Properties Rights
M	Month of the project (incl. deadlines for Deliverables and Milestones)
MS	Milestone
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PM	Person-month
PMT	Project management team
R	Report
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The purpose of this project management handbook is to provide the LuxHyVal partners with the main information needed to perform routine day-to-day project tasks and daily project management, as well as reoccurring standard procedures applied while developing and delivering project reports and deliverables, communication and disseminating the project materials and other results. This handbook can be updated during the project in case of changes to the described procedures or implementation of new practices.

The project management handbook is partially derived from clauses stated in the LuxHyVal Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement and comply with these documents. Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement take precedence over the project management handbook.

1.1. Consortium

The LuxHyVal Consortium brings together an international group of partners representing energy, industry, transport, **IT**, and academic fields, that are brought together to boost the penetration of hydrogen ecosystems in Luxembourg by deploying green hydrogen initiatives across the entire value chain from local production to utilization, including storage and distribution for a range of applications targeting industry and mobility, while also aiming to connect with existing/planned infrastructures.

The Consortium includes partner organizations from five EU member countries (Luxembourg, Germany, France, Czech Republic, and Spain), Eastern Europe (Ukraine), and Australia. The list of the LuxHyVal partners is given in **Table 1**.

Table 1. *The members of the LuxHyVal Consortium.*

N°	Abbreviation at LuxHyVal	Organization Full name	Country	Status	Role in the Project (the main task)
1	UL	University of Luxembourg	LU	COO	Coordination. Management
2	PW	Paul Wurth S.A.	LU	BEN	Planning and design of the infrastructure
3	ENC	Encevo S.A.	LU	BEN	Business case and ownership modelling
4	ENO	Enovos Luxembourg S.A.	LU	BEN	Deployment and commissioning of the infrastructure
5	LEN	LuxEnergie S.A.	LU	BEN	Operation and validation
6	SLA	Sales-Lentz S.A.	LU	BEN	H2 End-user: mobility/transport application
7	TICE	Syndicat des Tramways Intercommunaux dans le Canton d'Esch	LU	BEN	H2 End-user: mobility/transport application
8	LUXM	LuxMobility S.A.R.L.	LU	BEN	H2 End-user and advisor: mobility/transport application
9	CER	Ceratizit Luxembourg S.A.R.L.	LU	BEN	H2 End-user: industrial application/cemented carbide manufacturer
10	GPSS	Green Power Storage Solutions S.A.	LU	BEN	Energy Storage
11	LIST	Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology	LU	BEN	Digital Twinning

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12	IZES	Institut für Zukunftsenergie- und Stoffstromsysteme gGmbH	DE	BEN	Impact assessment and Public acceptance analysis
13	R2M	R2M Solution Spain S.L.	ES	BEN	Project communication, dissemination and exploitation, IPR protection
14	UB	University of Bordeaux	FR	BEN	Life Cycle Assessment
15	CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	FR	AE	Life Cycle Assessment
16	VSCHT	Vysoka Skola Chemicko- Technologicka v Prate	CZ	BEN	Follower Valley at Central Europe
17	KDU	Institute of Higher Education King Danylo University	UA	BEN	Follower Valley at Eastern Europe
18	UNSW	University of New South Wales	AU	AP	International Green H2 market assessment

1.2. Work Packages

The work plan consists of 8 Work Packages as illustrated on **Figure 1**.

Work package WP1: Project management and coordination [*Lead BEN: UL, M1 – M63*] encompass the financial, administrative, and contractual components, including the risk monitoring and mitigation during the project. Clear management structures and techniques are in place to build the framework for effortless implementation of LuxHyVal goals.

Figure 1. LuxHyVal WP structure.

Work package WP2: Business models, financial viability and inputs to regulation [*Lead BEN: ENC, M1 – M39*] develops the business case and ownership model for the LuxHyVal infrastructure that enables confident investment from stakeholders, engagement by end-users in contracts which deliver reliable and affordable green hydrogen. Different ownership models are considered, and several external factors are considered in the scenario assessment. Detailed feasibility study is completed as an input to the Engineering Design of WP3. Negotiations and agreements with offtakers regarding specific needs and conditions are carried out. Possible expansion of the business model with increased production is evaluated with international partners, with a particular view to international import of green hydrogen. Green hydrogen imports are explored, and findings shared with the Clean Hydrogen Mission. National regulations around supply and market support for green hydrogen are critically assessed and improvements, modifications and new regulation is proposed to relevant authorities.

Work package WP3: Planning and design of the LuxHyVal infrastructure [*Lead BEN: PW, M9 – M21*] focuses on the planning and design of all the components for the production (e.g., electrolyser), storage, distribution, connection to the existing and planned infrastructure, including connection to renewable energy sources, gas network, district heat grid and other networks.

Work package WP4: Deployment and commissioning of the LuxHyVal CHJU infrastructure [*Lead BEN: ENO, M22 – M33*] is composed of the work dedicated to deployment and commissioning of the entire hydrogen valley, including the production plant, storage, distribution and connection to the end-uses with the associated infrastructure. Activities focus on supply, construction, execution, project management and supervision with respect to civil and electrical works and installation of equipment. Permitting and approvals is obtained, while the safety plan is executed. Finally, the WP ensures commissioning and handover of all the components.

Work package WP5: Operation and validation of LuxHyVal with production, storage, distribution and uses [*Lead BEN: LEN, M34 – M53*] focuses on operation, monitoring and control of the valley to ensure optimal performance and great benefits. This includes the operation of all elements of LuxHyVal, the deployment and use of the Digital Twin for validation and real-time optimisation and the associated measurements. WP5 is the continuation of the deployment activities in WP4 and is strictly connected to the business model and market opportunities of WP2 and the comprehensive assessment of WP6.

Work package WP6: Comprehensive impact assessment and public acceptance [*Lead BEN: IZES, M10 – M57*] focuses on comprehensively assessing the impacts of the LuxHyVal on technical, economic, environmental and user acceptance. Specifically, in WP6 we assess technical and economic performance at component and system level; measure public understanding and increase acceptance of hydrogen technologies in Luxembourg; and investigate the benefits for energy system, mobility, industry and all involved stakeholders; and other tasks.

Work package WP7: Digital tools for optimization, upscaling and replication [*Lead BEN: LIST, M33 – M63*] contributes to the sustainability and scalability of the operation of the LuxHyVal system to facilitate its replication in other hydrogen valleys. For this purpose, we rely on the concept of a digital twin, which in our case describes the overall ecosystem of the LuxHyVal, from the power supply to the delivery of hydrogen to the end-users. However, the aim of our digital twin is not only to represent the real world and monitor its actual functioning, predict future tendencies but also to provide a means (visualisation) to enable the different stakeholders with decision support facility and evaluation of hypotheses about its improvement. In addition, an open architecture approach is followed to avoid vendor lock-in. In parallel, plans for upscaling the valley in other areas of LU and the Greater Regions are defined as well as specific replication plans in follower valleys in Central (i.e., CZ) and Eastern (i.e., UA) Europe with support from key stakeholders and associations from those countries.

Work package WP8 Exploitation, dissemination and communication [*Lead BEN: R2M, M1 – M63*] provides tools and support for ensuring great market impacts of the innovative solutions demonstrated in the Luxembourg Hydrogen Valley, underpinned by appropriate IPR management. Knowledge sharing, commercialisation and replication of results to the follower Valleys are promoted during the entire LuxHyVal via dedicated exploitation strategies to increase the potential for a fast market entry and replication.

2. Legal Documents

The documents regulating the LuxHyVal work process are LuxHyVal Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, annotated grant agreement, and reporting templates.

2.1. Grant Agreement

The LuxHyVal *Grant Agreement n°101111984* is composed of the Core text of 44 Articles and five Annexes:

- *Annex I, Part A*: Description of the Action: WPs' detailed description, tasks and leading partners; Staff efforts; Deliverables and Milestones; Risks. Some information was taken from the Original project proposal, uploaded to the EU portal, and automatically transferred to the Annex I-A.
- *Annex I, Part B*: Description of the Action: A descriptive part of the Original project proposal.
- *Annex II*: Estimated Budget for the Action
- *Annex II a*: Additional information on unit costs and contributions
- *Annex III*: Accession forms for Beneficiaries
- *Annex IV*: Model for the Financial Statement for a reporting period
- *Annex V*: Specific rules applied to Confidentiality and Security, Ethics, Values, IPR, Communication, etc.

The LuxHyVal Grant Agreement n°101111984 can be downloaded from the EU portal here [Participant Portal Grant Management Services \(europa.eu\)](#) (in the “Document Library” tab). As the document is not Public, your login data will be required.

2.2. Consortium Agreement

The LuxHyVal Consortium Agreement was negotiated and signed by all partners. It regulates the following aspects:

- management aspects, bodies and voting rules of the consortium,
- terms of access, ownership and the use of intellectual property (IP) generated in the project;
- ownership of results, and
- confidentiality of information.

The LuxHyVal Consortium Agreement can be found uploaded to the LuxHyVal MS Teams Channel. As the document is not Public, only the added to the channel participants are enabled access.

2.3. Supporting documents

Other useful documents and links are:

Annotated Grant Agreement (AGA) explains all articles of the Grant Agreement and provide sample calculations [aga_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

Continuous reporting on milestones and deliverables [Continuous reporting on milestones & deliverables - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#)

What and how to prepare for **checks, audits, reviews** and investigations [Checks, audits, reviews & investigations - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#)

3. Project Management

3.1. Project Management Structure

The structure of the LuxHyVal project management represents the roles LuxHyVal partners are carrying according to the defined work plan. The PM structure is shown on **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. LuxHyVal Project Management Structure.

Project management team (**Figure 3**) includes the Coordinator – UL (WP1 leader), and two partners acting as technical coordinators – Encevo S.A. (WP2 leader) and Paul Wurth S.A (WP3 leader).

Figure 3. LuxHyVal Project Management Team Structure.

Project Coordinator (Bradley P. Ladewig, UL) is responsible for the overall project and its objectives, quality, schedule, and budget. Together with the Project Manager, he is the contact point for the European Commission and chairs the Project Steering Committee. The detailed list of responsibilities of the Coordinator towards the Consortium and the EC are listed in the LuxHyVal CA, Chapter 6 “Governance structure”, subsection 6.4.2 of the Section 6.4 “Coordinator”.

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Project Manager (Anastasiia Gafiullina, UL): is responsible for the day-to-day coordination of the project on all questions except for the financial reporting, where the project manager is involved, however, the leading role belongs to **Project Financial Officer (Georgia Kaprou, UL)**. Contact details of the PMT will be given further in this document.

3.2. Internal communication

Internal Communication is the communication between members of the LuxHyVal Consortium (all project participants), regardless of their organization. The main channels used for internal communication are:

- Email
- MS Teams channel and the connected to it SharePoint depository
- Online conferences/calls (mainly MS Teams, but other programs are also accepted if preferred by participants)
- Phone calls
- Physical meetings

3.2.1. Emails and Contact List

Daily (routine) communication is based on emails or Teams/phone calls. Knowing the email of the person, you may give him/her a Teams call to discuss the issue. Working/mobile phone numbers will be covered further below in this section.

Requirements for emails:

- 1) Always start the subject with “LuxHyVal” to enable to search and find all the emails related to this project in the email folders. I.e., the **Subject** should look like: **LuxHyVal _ The actual topic**.
- 2) **Include project manager (at anastasiia.gafiullina@uni.lu) in the copy** for all relevant emails to keep the Coordinator updated on the actions/decisions. Here, relevant defines as any information the Coordinator should be aware of to successfully manage the project, any information that will cause changes in the project WPs, tasks, duration, risks, reflected in the deliverables, including reports, etc. However, it should never violate non-disclosure clauses. Additionally, if the email concerns LuxHyVal but the topic is only to be considered internally within your organization, no need to disclose it to the external participants.
- 3) Please, add to CC the following email: luxhyval@uni.lu – it also belongs to the Coordinator. Why doubling? We would like to store all LuxHyVal related emails in one place. Moreover, in case a new person is added to the Team, she/he will have a chance to access previous communication without a need to request it from other team members.

All persons involved in the LuxHyVal project are listed in the LuxHyVal Contact list (Excel spreadsheet) (1), LuxHyVal emailing list (2), and the MS Teams channel (3). These three channels contact list includes everyone, whether this person has already started to work on the tasks, or his/her tasks belong to a WP that is scheduled for later (according to the Gantt chart). That is to keep everyone informed and updated during the whole duration of the project.

The **Contact list** was created and shared with all the participants via email + it is stored in the “LuxHyVal” MS Teams channel in the folder “Communication” in the “Files” tab. This document is not provided here as it contains sensitive (private) information such as personal mobile phone numbers for some of the participants. Working phone numbers are also given in this contact spreadsheet, thus a call can be given along/instead of emails if this is the preference of the involved members.

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In case you need to **introduce a change to the Contact list**, send the request to the project manager at anastasiia.gafullina@uni.lu. We will make a change in the Contact list, Emailing list, and the MS Teams access.

3.2.2. MS Team Channel and File Storage

As mentioned above, all participants were added to the **MS Teams channel** titled “**LuxHyVal**”. This is to enable to schedule, record and store the recordings of all the [online/hybrid] Consortium meetings in one place (the meetings are in hybrid format due to the geography of Consortium members).

The MS Teams is also used as a platform for storing, sharing and collaborating on documents. Thus, collaborative writing is enabled by accessing the SharePoint site assigned to the Teams channel. Sensitive data (including survey data, interview transcripts, etc.) will be kept on internal servers of the project partners. The procedures will be described in detail in the D1.2 Data Management Plan to be submitted due M6.

3.3.Meetings

There are three main types of the meetings at the LuxHyVal project: reoccurring 6-months meetings (General Assembly meetings), monthly meetings, and meetings to perform WP tasks.

3.3.1. Reoccurring 6-months General Assembly meetings

These meetings are our obligation in the project.

Aim: Strategic level planning, comparison of the project status with the initial plan, aligning measures if needed. Decision making via voting if needed.

Who: Participation of the General Assembly is required, i.e., Coordinator + at least one representative from each Party. From the Coordinator’s side the principal coordinator, project manager and financial officer should be presented.

If someone’s attendance is not possible, the meeting recording will be stored at the MS Teams channel and can be viewed; the minutes will be sent to every project participant to notify about the **key** discussed topics and the decisions made.

Mode: 6-months meetings are very much preferred to be held with a physical presence, however under some circumstances remote participation is accepted. Thus, the mode is hybrid with the inclination towards participation in person.

Where: Location is to be decided to approx. 3 months prior to the meeting. The location should be comfortably assessable for the participants. Preferable location for the first part of the project is at or close to the premises of the Consortium members. For the second part of the project – that is when project-related construction works will be started in Luxembourg, – the location is planned to either be in Luxembourg.

3.3.2. Monthly Consortium meetings

Aim: Internal briefing. To update and align the partners on the project status, major steps in project progress and further steps, to discuss the rose issues and mitigation measures, to provide a summary of events, outreach, and public discussions. Decision making via GA voting if needed.

Who: Participation of the General Assembly is much preferred as decision-making process may happen. However, in this case you will be notify about it in the agenda. Obligatory for WP leaders and actual task

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leaders. Other participants may join if they would like to – we will send invitations to every person involved in the project to keep everyone updated on the progress.

If someone's attendance is not possible, the meeting recording will be stored at the MS Teams channel and can be viewed; the minutes will be sent to every project participant to notify about the **key** discussed topics and the decisions made.

Mode: to be held in a hybrid format. The Coordinator will organize a meeting space to accommodate those who would prefer to participate in person, others will join online.

Where: Online via MS Teams and on the Coordinator's premises.

For most of the meetings the venue is:

University of Luxembourg,
Campus Kirchberg, building B
6, rue Richard Coudenhove-Kalergi,
Luxemborg city, Luxembourg

Occasionally it may be held in Campus Belval on the address:

University of Luxembourg,
Campus Belval, Maison de Savoir (MSA) building
2, avenue de l'Université
Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg

The chosen venue will be sent along with the agenda a week prior to the meeting.

Agenda and Minutes: For the both 6-months and monthly meetings, the agenda is distributed prior to the meeting, and the minutes follows the meeting. The schedule for sending these documents, their content, and a possibility to add an item to the agenda are described in the LuxHyVal Consortium Agreement, Subsections 6.3.2 (scheduling a meeting and agenda) and 6.3.6 (minutes).

[*In short* on adding the item to the agenda: any Member may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all of the other Members no later than seven (7) calendar days preceding the meeting and two (2) days preceding an extraordinary meeting. Extraordinary meetings may be held upon request. Or simply to add a new item to the original agenda during the GA if agreed by simple majority].

The rules for making **decisions** that may take place **on the 6-months and monthly meetings**, i.e., voting rules and quorum are covered in the Subsection 6.3.4

[*Shortly:* the quorum is 2/3 of the GA; 1 member (Party) = 1 vote; APs are excluded from voting on some topics, mainly financial questions; Defaulting Party may not vote; decision is taken if 2/3 are agreed];

Followed by the **veto rights** in the subsection 6.3.5

[not covered *Shortly* as there are quite many important points, please, refer to the original CA];

Decisions made without a meeting are accepted if satisfy the requirements given in 6.3.3

[*Shortly:* the Coordinator circulates a suggested decision to every Party, 10 days to reply; the decision is agreed by 51% of all Members].

For **the list of all the decisions that are assigned to the General Assembly** to be made, please refer to the subsection 6.3.7. of the Consortium agreement.

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3.3.3. Meetings to perform WP tasks

Aim: To enable the participants to carry out tasks within work packages, exchange information, discuss the issues, define the detailed methodology.

How often: WP meetings can be quite frequently occurring if needed, e.g., bi-weekly meetings. However, this is to be decided by the WP leaders and to be agreed when planning each WP depending on the specificity of the tasks and the workload. The frequency of these meetings can be changed during the period of this WP if needed for better performance. Also, WP-meetings may be not pre-scheduled but organized upon request, however, with a prior notice.

Who: the WP leaders are mandatory to attend (those whose WPs are discussed/running), other participants who actually work on the tasks within those WPs and affected partners are strongly advised to attend (at least, one representative). Other may join upon their will and if it does not violate the non-disclosure of the confidential information clauses.

Mode: to be held in a hybrid format. The assigned WP leader will organize a meeting space to accommodate those who would prefer to participate in person, others will join online.

Where: Online via MS Teams and on the WP leader premises. The venue will be communicated in the agenda/invitation email if agenda is not applicable (for WP meetings the agenda is not mandatory).

4. External communication

External communication is a communication of the LuxHyVal participant on behalf of the project with non-members aimed on enhancing project visibility, disseminating project results through publications, a project website, conferences, workshops and other events, and the establishment of links to related projects.

4.1.Funding acknowledgement

All LuxHyVal communication activities (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) (**Figure 4**) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate). The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

No prior approval from the granting authority is required for the beneficiaries to use the emblem. (Section 17.2 “Visibility” in the GA).

Figure 4. The EU emblem for funding acknowledgement.

Additionally, the following disclaimer must be included: “Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the

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European Union or the Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them."

4.2. Logo

The logo of the LuxHyVal project is given in **Figure 5**. It should be included on all the presentation and communication materials. The logo in its various sizes and file-formats can be found in the MS Teams WP8 folder. The colors and font used in the logo are described in the visual identity guide.

Figure 5. The LuxHyVal logo.

4.3. Project website

The website of the project is available at <https://luxhyval.eu/> and presents the project. **Website content:**

- A **funding statement** is displayed on the landing page,
- **Summary** of the information about LuxHyVal project goals, value chain and fields we integrate, some of the targeted metrics,
- Project partners (**participants**),
- Our **contacts**: the mails for questions and our profiles on social networks (LinkedIn, Instagram),
- **Events**: past and upcoming. For upcoming event a simple registration form is planned,
- **News**: some quick overview from the past events, a note on passing a milestone when it happens, later on when the construction work is started there will be short updates on the status of the work, public deliverables,
- **Other Materials and Education**: notes from other media posted news about the LuxHyVal, materials from the organized workshops if any, a link to the relevant podcast episodes.

Some materials are displayed from the moment the website is launched (summary, partners, contacts), whereas the others (events, news, deliverables and other materials) will be added when ready. All the sections will be periodically updated.

4.4. Social Media Platforms

The LuxHyVal company's page on LinkedIn is accessible via the link <https://www.linkedin.com/company/luxhyval/>

Additionally, LuxHyVal presence will be built and communicated on Instagram with the account, the link to which will be given with the D8.1 due M4.

5. Document Management

5.1. Deliverable documents: Style, Naming and Structure

The MS Teams channel (SharePoint) contains the folder Deliverables (Files -> 08_Deliverables). One subfolder will be created for each deliverable, named as [yyyymmdd_Dn.m Name_vx.y], e.g., **20240130_D1.1 Project Management Handbook_v0.1**.

More specifically, in yyyymmdd_Dn.m Name_vx.y:

- **yyyymmdd** is the year month day
- **D** stands for “Deliverable”
- **n.m** is the Deliverable number (where “n” is the WP number and “m” is the number of the deliverable within this WP)
- **Name** is the title of the Deliverable
- **v** stands for “Version”
- **x.y** is the version number (see Section 5.3 for more details on how to identify the correct version)

Deliverables must use the Deliverable template. Its style (including fonts, colors, headers/footers, numbering of headings) and structure must be maintained. The following general structure should be followed and is as such provided in the deliverable template of the project:

- Cover page (project title, title of deliverable, date, lead beneficiary, authors, reviewers)
- Document Information and Revision History (information table, revision history table)
- Table of Contents
- Executive Summary
- List of Abbreviations
- The Core text
- Acknowledgements
- References (if applicable)
- Annexes (if applicable)

5.2. Templates for the Deliverables and Presentations

The templates for deliverables and presentations featuring the colors and font of the LuxHyVal logo, and include the required funding acknowledgment, can be found in the MS Teams channel -> Files -> 00_Templates.

All presentations that disseminate the results within the LuxHyVal project have to be made using the official LuxHyVal templates (not partner institution templates). Other templates may be used in case where only a part of the presented results is attributed to the LuxHyVal. However, on the LuxHyVal related slides the project logo should be shown, and the final slide must acknowledge the EU funding as described above.

5.3. Internal Review Process and Deadlines for Deliverables

The **deliverables should be prepared by the leading author**, representing the partner responsible for this deliverable. **All deliverables are reviewed internally by the Consortium**. Administrative deliverables are to be reviewed by all partners. Technical deliverables are to be reviewed by the project partners involved in the developing of this deliverable, whereas other partners may check the document and express their opinion. The purpose of the review is to ensure the consistency between the deliverable content and its provided summary, the objectives of the deliverable are met, the information provided is scientifically

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correct and of high-quality, to perform a proof-reading. All changes to the document, as well as comments, are given with the “track changes” mode on. When giving a comment or a request for correction, that would be a good practice to make the request/comment as clear as possible, indicate what is the point that is thought to be incorrect and provide the reviewers’ view on how it should be written. The lead author and his/her organization are responsible for addressing all comments given by all reviewers.

After being revised, the deliverables should be corrected by the leading author, representing the partner responsible for this deliverable. However, **after the revision** and correction process is over, **all deliverables are submitted by the project manager** on behalf of the project coordinator (**not** by the leading author!) to avoid confusion with the portal submission. The deliverable review and submission process follows the timeline indicated in the **Table 2**.

Table 2. *The timeline for the deliverable review and submission process.*

Deadlines before the Due date	
4 weeks (before DD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The draft of the Deliverable is uploaded for review to the MS Teams;- Reviewers are notified by the email that the document is ready to be reviewed;- The Consortium is notified by the email on the possibility to read and comment the document as well. <p>The reviewers and other members have 2 weeks to check and leave the comments.</p>
2 weeks	Reviewing round is closed. The draft revision and correction is started.
1 week	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- End of the first cycle of corrections;- The second round of revision if needed;- The Consortium approval.
2 days	Final version is ready and stored in the corresponding MS Teams folder.
Due date	The Deliverable is submitted to the EU portal by the Coordinator (project manager).

* As in the LuxHyVal Grant Agreement the deadlines for submission is given as months counting from the start of the project, “due date M6” (as a example) is considered as “by the end of the month 6”.

The rules applied to **document naming were given in the Section 5.1**. Here are the additional points on how the **version of the document** should be identified:

- **v0.1** – the first draft uploaded to the MS Teams for the review,
- **v0.2** – the version of the document after the first round of revision and corrections, i.e., the corrected **v0.1** (which is now ready to be checked at the round 2),
- **v0.n** – similar as above: the version that was changed after the round (n-1) revisions and now is ready to be reviewed at the n round,
- **v1.0** – the final version approved by the Consortium, which is to be submitted to the portal,
- **v2.0** – this is for the version updated after the EU revision if any.

While drafting, we **work with the same document without duplicating**. Only the **name changes according to the change in version** (v0.1 -> v0.2 -> v1.0, etc.). The **leading author** (as the main author of the document) **is responsible to ensure that the latest version is stored at the MS Teams folder**. The project manager (as responsible for the submission) informs the Consortium via email when the submission is done.

5.4. Other Files

Other documents and files include but are not limited to meeting materials (agenda, presentations, minutes), periodic and annual project reports, technical reports and papers, internal documents, etc. All documents are produced in English. If the document is a reference but was not produced as a part of the LuxHyVal project, the original language is kept.

The location is the MS Teams channel (SharePoint) -> Files -> a corresponding folder (it should be clear from the folder's title).

* Please, note that the documents are on that location, however, the templates are still on the MS Teams channel -> Files -> 00_Templates.

The files should be named as [yyyymmdd_Name_vx.y], e.g., **20240110_Minutes_Monthly meeting M-1_v1.0**. The naming and version control rules are the same as stated for the Deliverable documents.

6. Reporting to the European Commission (EC)

6.1. Continuous Reporting on SyGMa (EU portal)

The purpose of the continuous reporting is to provide the EC with the regular updates on the status of the project. The continuous reporting is available from the beginning of the project (opens before M1) and can be edited by all beneficiaries in SyGMa (System for Grant Management). More information is available on the portal, in "Online manual", here [Continuous reporting on milestones & deliverables - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#)

The continuous reporting includes the following sections:

- updates to the **publishable summary**
- updates on **researchers** involved in the project
- progress in **deliverables**
- progress in achieved **milestones**
- response to the **critical risks**
- **publications**
- **other achieved results**
- **dissemination and communications activities**
- **IPRs**

Each of these tabs provides a summary on the key information on the item to be reported such as the actual deadlines for the deliverables, milestones, etc., and the requirements for them. As the report is continuous, the information is filled in right in the portal once available.

Apart from the reporting continuously, there are three points when the continuous reporting should be compiled into a document – **the Intermediate progress report**, aimed on giving the intermediate summary of the activities carried out by each partner:

- 1) Intermediate progress report **1** is due month 11, by **30 September 2024**
- 2) Intermediate progress report **2** is due month 33, by **31 July 2026**
- 3) Intermediate progress report **3** is due month 55, by **31 May 2028**

Important notes on the project summary: there should be a separate summary for each periodic report, and it should be suitable for the direct publication by the Granting Authority, meaning being a stand-alone text, no references, easily understandable by a general audience, no longer than 2 pages, and with **no confidential/sensitive data**.

Important notes on the Communication and Dissemination updates: here the approach is to be more qualitative than a quantitative if other is not defined by the KPI for the corresponding deliverable. The main communication and dissemination activities should be described in the corresponding tabs (we should purpose, the targeted audience, status, KPIs if applicable and the actual metrics), especially when costs were charged to the project.

6.2.Periodic reporting: Technical and Financial reports

At the LuxHyVal, we have **four** periodic reports – **three Periodic reports** and **one Final report**. The periods are given below (from the GA, page 12). Each periodic (and the final) **report should be submitted within 60 days after the end of the period**. Hence, the deadlines for the Periodic reports are as such:

- Period 1: M1-M18 = November 2023 – April 2025; Periodic report **1** is due M20, **June 2025**
- Period 2: M19-M33 = May 2025 – July 2026; Periodic report **2** is due M35, **September 2026**
- Period 3: M34-M48 = August 2026 – October 2027; Periodic report **3** is due M50, **December 2027**
- Period 4: M49-M63 = November 2027 – August 2028; Final report **4** is due M65, **March 2029**

Each periodic report consists of two parts: the Technical Report (divided in turns into Parts A and B) and the Financial Report. What information is included in these documents? See below:

Technical Report, Part A: as it was with preparing the Grant Agreement, the Part A is the information filled into the portal and automatically extracted from there in the proper format. It includes the summary and objectives of the project, the worked performed from the beginning of the project till the reporting time, and overview on researchers involved, deliverables, milestones, critical risks, project impact, results and ownership, IPR, dissemination, etc.

Technical Report, Part B: again, as it was with preparing the Grant Agreement, the Part B is the descriptive part, which we write and upload to the portal as the prepared PDF document. It reflects the description and explanation of the work carried out within the work packages and deviations from the initial plan for the project (stated in the DoA, GA) if any.

The **Financial Report** is also generated automatically from the data previously added to the portal and consists of [here is the citation from the Online manual available on the portal]: “*the structured individual and consolidated Financial Statements (retrieved from the Grant Management System). In addition, most programmes require either a detailed cost reporting table (Excel table) or the use of resources report (online wizard) and, for payments above a certain threshold, a certificate on the financial statements (CFS)*”. (can be found here [Reports & payment requests - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#)). I.e., the financial report is composed of the financial statements of each partner’s cost claim for the closing reporting period.

The procedure for the Periodic report creation and submission:

- 1) As some information will be extracted from the Continuous reporting (goes to the technical report, part A), first **the Coordinator** should ensure that all tabs in Continuous reporting should be updated. This is important because once we continue with the technical reports, the information will be locked for some time, and there will be no possibility to add changes to this reporting period.
- 2) Filling in financial statement information (in Manage Project -> Periodic Reporting -> Financial Statement drafting) – **done by each partner**. The procedure follows the path: each beneficiary fills in the individual financial statement with the detailed eligible costs. Then it should be signed and submitted to the Coordinator. For this, the Beneficiary's PFSIGN needs to login to the portal, go to Manage Project -> Periodic Reporting -> Sign & Submit. No it is submitted to the Coordinator. **If not done on time, the expenses can be claimed to the next reporting period.**
* Affiliated Entities provide a blue ink signed Financial Statement paper to their Beneficiary; then the procedure is the same as described above.

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- 3) Preparing the Technical report, part B: **WP leaders report on their WP results and progress to the Coordinator** using a generic reporting template, provided by the Coordinator. The Project Coordinator compile the provided information into the Part B document. The document is reviewed by the LuxHyVal partners. Once approved, the Coordinator upload part B Technical as a PDF.
- 4) The **Coordinator** approves financial reports, and all accepted Financial Statements are included via Periodic Reporting -> Include tab. Not accepted Financial Statements can be sent back to a Partner for changes.
- 5) After Financial and Technical (A and B) parts are completed, the **Coordinator** (project manager) compile them into a single report and submit to the portal (-> submit to EU).

More details on the Periodic reporting can be found here [Reports & payment requests - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#).

6.3. Internal Reporting procedure and the Summary on the Reporting Dates

As for the both type of reports - Intermediate progress reports and Periodic reports – the Coordinator will need the information from the partners, here we set the deadlines for the internal reporting procedures. The WP leaders should ensure to gather the information about the technical progress in their WP from the assigned task leaders and compile a WP report that would be sent to the Coordinator. Any deviations to the DoE (Description of the Action, GA) should be explained and justified – we will need this information further in the reports to the EC.

To combine information on all the report the LuxHyVal should provide and the deadlines for their submission to the EC portal and – before that – to the Coordinator, the reporting calendar is presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3. *LuxHyVal reporting deadlines.*

Report type	The period	Due day to submit to the Coordinator	Due month for the report	Actual date to submit to the EC
Intermediate progress report 1	n.a.	n.a.	M11	30 September 2024
Periodic report 1	M1-M18 November 2023 – April 2025	M19 *one month after the end of the period = one month before the due date	M20	30 June 2025
Intermediate progress report 2	n.a.	n.a.	M33	31 July 2026
Periodic report 2	M19-M33 May 2025 – July 2026	M34	M35	30 September 2026
Periodic report 3	M34-M48 August 2026 – October 2027	M49	M50	31 December 2027
Intermediate progress report 3	n.a.	n.a.	M55	31 May 2028
Periodic report 4	M49-M63 November 2027 – January 2029	M64	M65	31 March 2029

